

SPIDER

EU-LAC Digital Partnership

D.3.1 - Terms of Reference of the EU-LAC Digital Dialogues Implementation Forum

Grant Agreement Number: 101135861

Project Acronym: SPIDER

Funding Scheme: Coordination and Support Action

Due date: 31/01/2024

Actual date: 31/01/2024

Document author/s: INMARK

Version: 1.0

Dissemination level: PU

Status: Final Version

Document History			
Version	Date	Comments	Author
0.1	15/01/24	Structure of ToR	Yolanda Ursa, Eugenia Peñaloza, INMARK
0.2	19/01/24	First draft	Yolanda Ursa, Luciana Ayciriex, INMARK
0.3	26/01/24	First draft revision	Maria F. Cabrera, UPM
1.0	31/01/24	Final version	Yolanda Ursa, INMARK

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

BELLA	Building the Europe link to Latin America
CELAC	Community of Latin American and Caribbean States
CoC	Community of Practice
DEI	Diversity, Equality and Inclusion
DIF	EU-LAC Digital Dialogues Implementation Forum
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GEANT	pan-European research and education network.
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
LAC	Latin America and Caribbean countries
NREN	National Research and Education Network
RedCLARA	South American research & education network
R&I	Research and Innovation
RFO	Research Funding Organisation
RPO	Research Performing Organisation
STI	Science, Technology and Innovation
ToR	Terms of Reference
WG	Working Group

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

A core element of the SPIDER project is the establishment of the “EU-LAC Digital Dialogues Implementation Forum” (short name: DIF) that will act as a multi-stakeholder mechanism to foster dialogues, promote policy debate and facilitate the exchange of information and best practices to support the implementation of R&I commitments resulting from EU-LAC digital dialogues.

Under the umbrella of the DIF, two dedicated and complementary Working Groups (WGs) will be established:

WG1: Human-centric digital transformation: Focuses on the adoption of a human-centred approach to technology development in alignment with social and ethical values. This WG will prepare the ground to discuss the different elements that will allow EU-LAC strategic partnerships to enable a human-centred digital transformation. The debate includes, but it is not limited to:

- Principles guiding the implementation of joint digital initiatives.
- Exploitation of personal data in the use of technologies.
- Large-scale cybersecurity, data breaches, trust and online disinformation.

WG2: DEI - Diversity, Equality and Inclusion: Promotes an effective application of DEI principles and values to EU-LAC cooperation on digital transformation. Discussion of the WG2 will include but not limited to:

- Capabilities needed to facilitate the integration of intersectional gender dimension into R&I content.
- DEI in the research design process.
- Research expertise or other type of support for research teams in the digital ecosystem of LAC and Europe.

This report (Deliverable D3.1) presents the Terms of Reference of the EU-LAC Digital Dialogues Implementation Forum, which outlines the purpose, structure, membership and operation of the DIF.

1. INTRODUCTION

The SPIDER project [long name: EU-LAC Strategic Partnership for the Implementation of Digital Dialogues in R&I Cooperation] aims to support the exploitation of the full potential of the [BELLA network](#) and the implementation of the outcomes of EU-LAC dialogues in the context of digitalisation and R&I.

SPIDER proposes a multi-stakeholder perspective to enable the development of an EU-LAC strategic partnership. SPIDER will engage relevant R&I stakeholders from EU and LAC more actively and strategically in supporting dialogues and creating a common and orchestrated vision and strategy for the exploitation of the full potential of the BELLA network and the implementation of the outcomes of digital dialogues to enhance EU-LAC cooperation in R&I.

SPIDER has the following core objectives:

#O1. Provide a framework for enhancing EU-LAC cooperation on R&I. SPIDER will produce a mapping of the digital transformation landscape, including EU and LAC policies, strategies and funding programmes for international cooperation in R&I and identify the scope of current digital dialogues and agreements between Europe and BELLA countries in LAC.

#O2. Maximise and promote the potential of BELLA network for R&I cooperation and ensure the sustainable use of the infrastructure by stimulating the adoption and use of digital transformation technologies, such as Artificial Intelligence/Machine Learning, Mobile (5G/6G), Blockchain, Cloud Computing, High Performance Computing, Cybersecurity tools and technologies and Virtual Research Environments (e.g. virtual laboratories, simulators, science gateways, data repositories).

#O3. Launch the EU-LAC Digital Dialogues Implementation Forum (DIF) that will act as a multi-stakeholder mechanism to foster dialogues, promote policy debate and facilitate the exchange of information and best practices to support the implementation of R&I commitments resulting from EU-LAC digital dialogues.

#O4. Establish a Twinning Programme to support the development of digital partnerships and new business opportunities benefiting from BELLA infrastructure and addressing its challenges.

#O5. Increase visibility of the project actions, awareness raising and engagement with relevant stakeholders from EU and LAC. SPIDER will engage with influential decision makers and stakeholders, including researchers, innovators, technologists, policy makers and thought leaders through a cascade of events, focus groups, call for ideas, Dialogue Forum events, webinars and workshops, demo-days and a final conference.

At the core of the SPIDER strategy and covered in Objective 3 is the EU-LAC Digital Dialogues Implementation Forum (DIF) that will be established as a multi-stakeholder platform to foster dialogues, promote policy debate and facilitate the exchange of information and best practices, and ultimately to support the implementation of R&I commitments resulting from EU-LAC digital dialogues.

This task will set out the Terms of Reference, including the definition of the operational structure and composition of the EU-LAC Digital Dialogues Implementation Forum (DIF) and its Working Groups. The DIF members and activities will be accessible from the SPIDER website www.spidernetwork.org.

2. EU-LAC DIGITAL DIALOGUES IMPLEMENTATION FORUM – DIF

2.1. Objectives

The DIF will pursue the following objectives:

- To proactively support the implementation of EU-LAC digital dialogues' commitments;
- To establish Working Groups to support coordination of policies and R&I efforts underway in the area of human centred digital transformation, alongside inclusiveness and sustainability;
- To organise Dialogue Forum events to share ideas and best practices for the implementation of EU-LAC digital dialogues' agreements;
- To create the SPIDER Community of Practice (CoP); OB3.5 To develop a roadmap for future EU-LAC cooperation on digital transformation.

2.2. Working Groups Structure

The DIF will be comprised of two complementary and result oriented WGs that will be set up in month 3 of the project. The WGs will function regularly and consistently to achieve scoping, recruitment, readiness, participation and input for Dialogue Forum events. Furthermore, the WGs will provide inputs to set up the roadmap and recommendations to support the implementation of EU-LAC dialogues' commitments.

WG1: Human-centric digital transformation.

WG1 will support a human-centred approach to technology development that is aligned with European social and ethical values. This WG will prepare the ground to debate which are the different ingredients that will allow strategic partnerships to enable a human-centred transformation. The principles guiding the implementation of joint digital initiatives will also be discussed. As the issue of trust has become central in the use of technologies, WG1 will also discuss the exploitation of personal data, large-scale cybersecurity, data breaches, online disinformation and growing awareness in this matter.

These developments in digital and enabling technologies have the potential to enhance social inclusion and ensure a two-way engagement with society. In this spirit, WG1 will host Dialogue Forum sessions to discuss how to promote a human-centred digital transformation in the context of EU-LAC relations and to gather views on the principles that should guide joint digital initiatives.

WG2: DEI - Diversity, Equality and Inclusion

WG2 will promote an effective application of DEI principles and values to EU-LAC cooperation on digital transformation. Discussion of the WG2 will enhance understanding of what kind of capabilities are needed to facilitate the integration of intersectional gender dimension into R&I content. Such capabilities could be, for example, assessment of the research design, research expertise or other type of support for research teams in the digital ecosystem of LAC and Europe. Leaders of the Women TechEU initiative, the EIC Women Leadership Programme, in partnership with EIT and EurA, and the EU-LAC Women's International Network will be invited to join the DEI WG.

2.3. Membership

The DIF will bring together relevant policy and practitioners, actors of the digital ecosystem of science, technology, education and innovation in EU and LAC, including dialogues’ decision makers, NRENs, RFOs, RPOs, digital and ICT companies, among others. The WGs membership will be composed of well-known key actors of the digital ecosystem in EU and LAC. The members of the WGs will be shown on the SPIDER website, specifically on the sites of each WG, where these profiles will be presented along with their LinkedIn profiles to make their background and expertise available for those interested in knowing more about the DIF and its members.

The SPIDER project members are in the process of identifying, recruiting and populating the working groups with new members and expect to have these filled in Quarter 1 of 2024, in a worksheet (presented below) where experts will be organized based on the WG and region they belong to when a full complement of members should have indicated their willingness to participate.

They will function regularly and consistently to achieve scoping, recruitment, readiness, participation and input for Dialogue Forum events and support to the implementation of EU-LAC digital dialogues commitments.

Figure 1 – Composition of the 2 Working Groups of the DIF

2.4. Operational functioning

Under the leadership of the SPIDER consortium, these Working Groups will come together to collectively identify main challenges to champion a human-centred approach and DEI values to digital transformation. At the same time the DIF WGs will provide opinions and recommendations for the practical implementation of the commitments resulting from EU-LAC digital dialogues across the BELLA countries in LAC, and thus increase R&I transatlantic cooperation.

The DIF, through its WGs, will bring together high-level experts from both sides of the Atlantic (at least 30 from outside the consortium during the project life cycle) that will be called upon either through online meetings or relevant activities during the project.

The WGs will each address specific issues to foster a human-centred digital transformation built on DEI principles and supported by the BELLA potential and EU-LAC digital dialogues for R&I collaboration.

They will deliver input for Policy Briefs with recommendations to enhance evolving digital dialogues between the EU and LAC, and thus significantly contribute to reinforce the political and technological framework for possible EU-LAC cooperation in R&I.

Systematic information will be gathered through insights from focus groups with key stakeholders in the WGs from EU and LAC. Major features of the mapping on digital transformation landscape, including EU and LAC policies, strategies and funding programmes for international cooperation in R&I and the scope of current digital dialogues and agreements between Europe and BELLA countries in LAC, will serve as input to the DIF and will be disseminated through SPIDER's website, social media profiles ([LinkedIn](#) and [X](#)), newsletter, policy briefs and a final conference.

2.5. Activities

The Terms of Reference of the DIF include the involvement of the WGs in key project activities:

- **Dialogue Forum Events**

The members of the WGs of the DIF will come together in annual Dialogue Forum events. The Dialogue Forum will provide an inclusive space for dialogue and co-creation, thus facilitating policy discussion and cooperation in actions to implement digital transformation's commitments thanks to the connection and engagement with R&I actors.

- **Roadmap for future EU-LAC cooperation on digital transformation**

The WGs will provide inputs to set up the roadmap and recommendations to support the implementation of EU-LAC dialogues' commitments. Through the Dialogue Forum events, the WGs will feed the process of developing a roadmap for future cooperation on digital transformation between EU and LAC, taking advantage of the BELLA network. The roadmap will serve as a reference document for policy makers, providing input for future strategic roadmaps on cooperation in STI between Europe and the members of the Community of Latin American and Caribbean States (CELAC).

- **SPIDER Community of Practice**

Members of the WGs and will join the SPIDER Community of Practice (CoP), whose members will act as ambassadors to disseminate the benefits of adopting an inclusive and human-centred digital approach to build strategic partnerships for

transatlantic cooperation and help scale up the experience on the use of BELLA across LAC and Europe. The CoP will bring together relevant actors from both sides of the Atlantic, including stakeholders from academia (NRENs, Universities, Research centres, centres of excellence) and industry, policy makers, investors, etc.

- **SPIDER Ambassadors**

An ambassador program will be established for WG members, empowering them with the authority to effectively communicate notable achievements of the DIF and champion SPIDER's vision, values, and initiatives. This initiative aims not only to enhance the visibility of both ambassadors and the DIF but also to foster connections with new, pertinent stakeholders in a more personable manner. This approach directly contributes to bolstering DIF's credibility.

- **Synergies with other R&I networks and initiatives**

In addition, the DIF will contribute to consolidate the EU-LAC digital partnership by creating synergies and increasing coordination and cooperation with other networks and initiatives, including BELLA, RedCLARA and GEANT communities, digital innovation hubs, ENRICH in LAC and the EU-LAC Digital Alliance, among others.

Altogether, these activities will guide work of the WGs. This in turn will feed into the required input for the roadmap, output for the policy briefs and recommendations to practical implementation of R&I commitments resulting from EU-LAC digital dialogues.

2.6. *Benefits of participation*

There are several key **benefits** to involvement as part of the EU-LAC DIF Working Groups, including:

- **Frequent interactions** with like-minded WG Members on both sides of the Atlantic working on technology areas that can benefit from the use of BELLA (e.g. AI, 5G, Blockchain, Cloud Computing, HPC, Cybersecurity and Virtual Research Environments), and adopting a human-centric approach and DEI principles, which could lead to early and fruitful partnership building in future R&I cooperation projects;
- **Working together in a larger group** will enable the decision makers in the funding agencies involved in the EU-LAC Policy dialogues to gather information from a larger comprehensive group of stakeholders and will take greater notice of WGs suggested **contributions on areas** of mutually beneficial cooperation in transatlantic topics **that require future EU-LAC funding mechanisms**;
- **Early access to the outcomes and commitments of EU-LAC dialogues**, while they are being written prior to completion submitted to funding bodies, enabling early intervention and contribution to the draft papers;
- **Bringing together** of the **research and innovation and policy stakeholders** working towards a common goal and **bridging the gap** that currently exists between the political agreements and commitments emerging from these dialogues and their practical implementation
- It is expected that the WGs members will be a **good channel of information exchange** with regular updates in these fast-moving technology areas for digital transformation that can benefit from the use of the BELLA infrastructure at regional and local level, which will be of significant benefit to the other members;
- **The Members' work will be disseminated and highlighted** regularly to both the funding and decision makers and the wider R&I and Policy communities **via the**

project's dissemination channels: SPIDER's website, social media profiles and newsletter

2.7. Timeline and expectations on members

The SPIDER project commenced on 1st November 2023 and the duration of the project is 30 months. During these two years and a half timeframe, or as long as required, the WGs will remain active, yet dynamic, i.e. picking up new members from EU and LAC that will be invited to participate in Dialogue Forum events, focus groups, workshops, final conference and other events organized by the SPIDER consortium to engage with relevant stakeholders and active communities on both sides of the Atlantic.

The scheduling of the project events in an online or hybrid format will facilitate the virtual participation from both sides of the Atlantic and thus a more dynamic form of interactions with the SPIDER WG members.

The SPIDER project will leverage the expertise of the project partners and external WG members' in EU-LAC dialogues and R&I cooperation, including the promotion of values for an inclusive human-centric digital transformation.

To support these activities, the WG will also investigate and track on a regular basis external groups, initiatives, events to link/liaise with at EU and LAC level, for greater impact, dissemination and also to identify synergies and potential areas for collaboration and knowledge sharing, including technology areas that can benefit from BELLA as already identified by SPIDER. Such current identified initiatives would include collaboration with BELLA, RedCLARA and GEANT communities, as well as with the EU-LAC Digital Alliance, and other initiatives.

Suitable dialogues and digital transformation focused events to target will also be considered on a regular basis, to assess possible dissemination opportunities and visible involvement of the SPIDER project and other EU and LAC collaborative projects to promote the activities and the outputs from the Working Groups.

For all meetings and events, all participants will be informed with enough time in advance, for planning arrangements to be made.

2.8. Time involved

The participation of members in the SPIDER working groups is on a voluntary basis, but active involvement is necessary to be successful. Nevertheless, SPIDER consortium wishes to interfere minimally with the participants' usual day to day responsibilities. Thus, the foreseen workload of the working group is estimated to be about a few hours per month, and it is expected that this work should also be part of members' own projects or organisations' events participation, active dissemination, and other collaboration activities and SPIDER will raise awareness of WGs members role on a continual basis, highlighting their good work in the WG.

2.9. Immediate next steps

We are in the process of identifying, recruiting and populating the working groups with new members and expect to have this activity fulfilled in March 2024, when a full set of members should have indicated their willingness to participate. We expect to have at least 15 members per WG, with a balance from EU and LAC in each WG.

We have currently identified over 30 members for the two WGs and are in the initial stages of making contact with them with a view to identifying potential participants to the upcoming Dialogue Forum events.

In addition, the SPIDER consortium has established a strong connection with BELLA and will discuss the potential events in which the DIF WGs members can participate to maximise impact.

3. CONCLUSION

This document sets out the Terms of Reference of the SPIDER EU-LAC Digital Dialogues Implementation Forum (DIF) comprised of two dedicated working groups:

WG1. Human-centric digital transformation, exploring the potential of human-centred digital transformation to build an EU-LAC digital partnership across technology areas that can benefit from the use of BELLA network, such as Artificial Intelligence/Machine Learning, Mobile (5G/6G), Blockchain, Cloud Computing, High Performance Computing, Cybersecurity tools and technologies and Virtual Research Environments (e.g. virtual laboratories, simulators, science gateways, data repositories).

WG2. DEI - Diversity, Equality and Inclusion: exploring the application of DEI principles and values to EU-LAC cooperation on digital transformation.

Both WGs' topics are of mutual importance to EU and LAC, which would greatly benefit the WG members themselves, the wider R&I community and contribute significantly to the exploitation of BELLA and to the practical implementation of EU-LAC policy dialogues' commitments by supporting the adoption of a human-centred and inclusive perspective to effectively increase digital cooperation in R&I.

The document details the structure, membership, activities, operations, benefits to participation, and foreseen high-level timelines of the activities of the WGs, as the details are still being discussed on the project level.

The project members are already in the process of identifying, recruiting and populating the working groups with new members and expect to have these filled in Quarter 1 of 2024, when a full complement of members should have indicated their willingness to participate. We expect to have at least 15 members per WG, with a balance from EU and LAC in each WG.

At the time of publication of this report, we have currently identified over 30 members for the two WGs in both human-centric digital transformation and DEI and are in the initial stages of making contact with them with a view to organizing the series of Dialogue Forum events.

These Terms of Reference will be shared with the potential members upon invitation to the WGs and any uncertainties about the expectations from the WG members will be addressed on a case by case basis, and, if needed, the ToR document will be updated accordingly.